

UK Sensitive Data Research Infrastructure Landscape Review 2025

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1 Public summary

A lot of the research that helps improve public services in the UK – for example, education, healthcare or housing services – relies on information about people and communities. Because much of that information is about people, it is sensitive, so it cannot simply be emailed around or downloaded onto personal computers. Trusted Research Environments are one way the UK makes it possible for approved researchers to use sensitive data safely, for research that benefits the public.

WHAT IS A TRUSTED RESEARCH ENVIRONMENT (TRE)?

A TRE is a highly secure computing environment where approved researchers can log in to analyse sensitive datasets to advance research for public benefit. The source data stays inside the TRE: anything researchers want to take out (like summary results, charts or tables) is checked to make sure it does not reveal information about any individual. TREs also keep records of who accessed what, and when, and operate under strict rules and oversight.

WHAT IS SENSITIVE DATA?

In this report, sensitive data includes information that could identify a person (directly or indirectly) or reveal something private or confidential. This can include social care and education information, health records, or detailed survey responses, for example. Even when obvious identifiers like names and addresses are removed, data can still be sensitive if there is a risk someone could be identified by combining it with other data sources. Some commercial or confidential business information can also be sensitive.

WHAT IS DARE UK?

DARE UK (Data and Analytics Research Environments UK) is a programme that aims to establish a safe and collaborative network of TREs. It brings together organisations across the UK to improve how researchers can access and use data securely. It aims to encourage consistent standards, new TRE capabilities and good governance, and enable public confidence.

WHY THIS LANDSCAPE REVIEW?

Between April and September 2025, DARE UK put out a survey for organisations involved in providing or supporting TREs and related services for sensitive data research. This report summarises what 63 organisations across universities, the public sector, charities and the private sector told us about how TREs are operating in the UK. It explores what capabilities they offer, how they are funded, how they keep data safe and how they involve and engage the public. This survey provides self-reported data from TREs without independent verification of their responses.

1.1 Key findings

The UK has a large and growing TRE ecosystem. In 2025, the 63 organisations who replied to our survey supported at least around 6,700 active research projects using sensitive data.

Universities and the public sector are central: 49 out of the 63 organisations (78%) were academic or public sector, showing that most TRE activity and investment sits in publicly oriented organisations.

TREs exist across the UK, but capacity is uneven. Respondents reported sites in all four nations, with a strong concentration in London and several English regions, alongside important national and regional services in Scotland, Wales and Northern Ireland.

Many organisations play more than one role and may provide both data and other related services. The same organisation may help host the secure system, manage access for researchers and supply datasets. Altogether, 48 out of 63 organisations (76%) classed themselves as TRE service providers.

Linking different sources of data from across sectors is growing, but not yet routine. Nearly half of the TRE service providers (22 of 48) said that fewer than 10% of their projects use “cross-domain” data (for example, linking health with education or employment data). However, around one in five TREs reported that most of their work is cross-domain, suggesting this is an expanding area.

Training of Artificial Intelligence (AI) is increasingly supported. About 69% of TRE service providers (33 of 48) said they provide tools that help researchers train AI or machine learning models. Access to specialist computing has increased since the previous survey.

Most TRE service providers (45 of 48; 94%) enforce technical controls that prevent researchers from freely downloading data. Instead, any results intended for export must be placed in an “airlock,” where they undergo review to ensure that analytical outputs do not compromise individual privacy. Our survey indicates that this output-checking process is still largely manual: most TREs rely on expert staff to conduct reviews, with only a minority supplementing this work with semi-automated tools. None of the respondents reported using fully automated review systems.

Funding for TREs and data providers largely comes from public sources, and staff time is a major cost. Around 65% of all respondents (41 of 63) reported public grants as a funding source, with staff costs making up more than half of annual costs for nearly two-thirds.

Public involvement is widely recognised, but varies in depth. Over half of respondents said they carry out public involvement and engagement activities at least quarterly, but resources and approaches differ substantially between organisations.

Standards and accreditation are common and still expanding. Many TREs use recognised security and governance standards, and awareness of the DARE UK-funded Standardised Architecture for Trusted Research Environments (SATRE) is high (84%), with 45% of TREs benchmarking themselves against the SATRE standard.

WHY DO THESE FINDINGS MATTER?

TREs are part of the UK’s approach to using sensitive data responsibly: protecting privacy while enabling research that can inform public services and policy decisions to improve lives.

With safe access to sensitive data for research, we can better understand and respond to some of the UK’s most pressing societal challenges, such as rising social inequality and climate change.

This landscape review shows a sector that is becoming more capable and more connected, but still uneven in resources and maturity. It also highlights practical areas where the UK can keep improving, such as making it easier to do secure research across different TREs; strengthening long-term funding and workforce capacity; and supporting meaningful public involvement in decisions about how data is used.

2 Executive summary

Between April and September 2025, DARE UK ran an open survey of research infrastructures in the domain of sensitive data across the UK. Of the 63 organisations who responded, 48 (76%) identified as Trusted Research Environments (TREs).

This report summarises the responses from TREs regarding their overall capabilities, clarifies their distinct organisational roles, examines funding and sustainability models, and explores approaches to governance, technology and public involvement. It brings together insights from organisations including universities, government agencies, charities and private sector providers to present a picture of how the UK's sensitive data research ecosystem is evolving.

2.1 Landscape overview

Overall, the survey received responses from most of the large regional or national TRE services in the UK, including:

- 11 of 12 NHS national and regional Secure Data Environments in England
- All five members of the Scottish Safe Haven Network in Scotland
- The SAIL Databank as the national TRE in Wales
- The Northern Ireland Honest Broker Service in Northern Ireland
- UK-wide data research infrastructures such as the ONS Secure Research Service, UK Data Service, UK Biobank, OurFutureHealth and OpenSAFELY

Beyond these larger services, we received responses from around 40 smaller providers across the landscape.

Academic institutions and public sector organisations remain the backbone of the TRE landscape, representing the bulk of activity and investment; 49 out of the 63 organisations (78%) were academic or public sector. The TRE ecosystem spans all four nations of the UK, with respondents reporting sites in England (40 of 63; 63%), Scotland (9 of 63; 14%), Wales (1 of 63; 2%) and Northern Ireland (3 of 63; 5%), alongside a significant share with sites in multiple nations (10 of 63; 16%). The regional distribution therein indicates a strong centralisation of research infrastructure in London and a handful of English regions, balanced by strategic nodes in Scotland, Wales and Northern Ireland.

TRE Service Providers – organisations that manage and operate TREs – comprised the bulk of respondents (48 of 63; 76%) to this review. Thirty-four of these TRE Service Providers (71%) also consider themselves as having additional roles as either Data Provider, Platform Provider or both. We define Data Provider as a role that provides research-ready data but does not provide analysis services, and Platform Provider as a role that provides underpinning hardware, software and networking but again, does not offer a TRE service to users.

TRE Service Providers supported an estimated lower bound of 6,700 active UK projects using sensitive data in 2025 alongside a healthy research user base, although placing a figure on users is difficult without any way to estimate the potential overlaps in users across providers. Suffice to say there is an actively engaged research user base driving the demand for TRE services, with a notable increase at the lower ranges of user counts likely as a result of a cohort of 'newer' TREs maturing over the last few years.

This review indicates that, while cross-domain data use is emerging, it is not yet widespread across the TRE landscape. Almost half of Service Providers (22 of 48; 46%) indicated that fewer than 10% of their projects involve cross-domain data. Nearly one in five TRE Service Providers (9 of 48; 19%), however, do engage in high levels of cross-domain research, where the majority of the projects they host combine datasets from multiple sectors. The presence of a growing minority engaging in multi-domain research suggests increasing capability and interest in this area, which could become a key feature of the TRE ecosystem as interoperability, federated analysis and data-sharing frameworks continue to mature.

2025 DARE UK TRE SURVEY RESPONDENTS

2.2 Tools and technology

Technological maturity is improving steadily, with more TRE Service Providers providing computational tools beyond the classic “desktop plus stats package” model. The vast majority (41 of 48; 85%) support the open-source R and Python development environments, and many TRE Service Providers now offer containerisation tools for flexibility: 25 of 48 (52%) support containerised workloads and 10 of 48 (20%) offer users a “bring your own container” service. In general, most TRE Service Providers (38 of 48; 80%) support user requests for the installation of new software.

A majority of TRE Service Providers (33 of 48; 69%) provide software tooling to support the training of artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML) models. However, advanced features such as workflow automation and federated analysis are still developing, suggesting that technical interoperability within and between TREs remains a work in progress. Around 20% of TRE Service Providers (10 of 48) offer support for internal workflow tools, with most of those being tools native to the underlying platform environment. Only 12 of the 48 TRE Service Providers (25%) support any kind of inter-service federation, and the majority of those are in trial or pilot phases.

42 of 48 TRE Service Providers (88%) reported employing staff who are independent of the research teams to review files for potential disclosure risks prior to export from the environment. A further three (6%) rely on members of the research team – often the project’s principal investigator – to undertake disclosure control checks. The remaining 6% of TRE Service Providers either did not answer or selected “Other”.

Manual review remains the predominant approach to statistical disclosure control: 33 of 48 of TRE Service Providers (69%) operate an entirely manual process, while nine (19%) supplement manual review with semi-automated tools. No respondents reported using fully automated disclosure control systems of the type required to enable fully federated analytics or federated machine learning across multiple TREs. Disclosure control of trained AI models requires automated as well as manual review – thus, these responses indicate that disclosure control of trained AI models remains a challenge for TREs¹.

In terms of TRE platform infrastructure in use by Service Providers, 14 of 48 (29%) reported using public cloud platforms exclusively, with 13 (27%) running their own infrastructure entirely on-premises, 10 (21%) using specialist TRE Platform Providers, and the balance reporting various hybrid combinations of these three. Just over half of TRE Service Providers (25 of 48; 52%) offer some kind of high-performance computing environment for their users.

2.3 Funding

Funding models are broad-based but continue to rely heavily on public grants, reported by 65% of all organisations who responded (41 of 63), while private-sector funding was reported as a source by only 27% (17 of 63). The top five public funding sources reported were the Medical Research Council (reported by 35 of 63; 56%), the Economic and Social Research Council (22 of 63; 35%), Innovate UK (14 of 63; 22%), the Engineering and Physical Sciences Research Council (9 of 63; 14%) and the National Institute for Health and Care Research (8 of 63; 13%).

The dominant cost in the sector is people, with staff accounting for more than half of annual costs in nearly two-thirds of respondents (63%).

2.4 Public involvement and engagement

Public involvement and engagement (PIE) are now recognised as essential to demonstrating trustworthiness, with over half of respondents (35 of 63; 56%) reporting “regular” PIE activities on at least a quarterly basis. The depth and consistency of these activities, however, vary widely; just over half of respondents reported having dedicated budgets for PIE, and a third reported having no dedicated funding and running PIE on an ad hoc basis only. Many TREs run workshops, consultations and outreach sessions to promote transparency. Most respondents have adopted some form of measurement to understand the impact and influence of their PIE activities, though approaches remain diverse and, in many cases, are still evolving.

2.5 Standards and accreditation

The survey highlights a continuing emphasis on standards and accreditation, with most organisations adopting recognised frameworks such as ISO 27001 (38 of 63; 61%), the NHS Data Security and Protection Toolkit (45 of 63; 71%), the Digital Economy Act 2017 (DEA 2017) (10 of 63; 16%) and the emerging Standardised Architecture for Trusted Research Environments (SATRE) (28 of 63; 45%), the development of which has been funded by DARE UK since 2023. Over a quarter of respondents indicated a desire to pursue accreditation in the coming year, primarily ISO 27001 certification (18 of 63; 29%), with a few aiming for accreditation as processors under DEA 2017 (11 of 63; 17%). Encouragingly, perhaps, awareness of the SATRE specification is high (53 of 63; 84%). These efforts reflect a collective drive toward improving data management, interoperability and accountability.

2.6 Overarching trends

Between this survey and our previous survey (2023) four trends are worth highlighting.

- Infrastructure provision among TRE Service Providers has seen two shifts: a notable increase in the use of specialist Platform Providers, either stand-alone or in combination with other platforms (from 16% to 40%); and an increase of five percentage points in pure on-premises implementations (from 22% to 27%)
- Projects hosted by TRE Service Providers involving “smart data” – social media, wearables, mobile phone, internet use – form a new category in this review and were reported by 29% of TREs. Among other data types, projects involving health data have remained high (89% in 2023 vs 88% in this survey), use of commercial data is slightly increased (22% to 29%) and both administrative and “other” data have seen significant increases in their use (53% to 67% and 4% to 23% respectively)
- The “other” category of projects in the 2025 survey shows a significant increase in the use of medical imaging and omics data
- The share of TRE Service Providers offering advanced capabilities in high performance computing (HPC) and graphics processing units (GPUs) for more specialised, high-capacity processing demands has increased overall. There has been a slight increase for HPC (47% to 51%) and a significant increase for GPU (47% to 70%)

Overall, the TRE landscape is showing progress toward a standardised, collaborative research environment. Nevertheless, disparities in resources, technical capacity and engagement practice persist across sectors and regions. The findings suggest that stronger national coordination, investment in infrastructure and skills, and clearer pathways for public participation will be essential to achieving a fully connected, transparent and sustainable UK TRE ecosystem.

¹Through private communications, we are aware that significant challenges remain in assessing the disclosure risks of machine learning models created within TREs. This remains an active area of research and development.

3 Glossary of key terms

Accreditation

Formal certification showing that an organisation meets recognised security and data-protection standards.

Artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML)

Computer techniques that allow systems to learn patterns from data and make predictions or decisions, often used in data-intensive research.

Containerisation (e.g. Docker)

A way of packaging software and analysis tools so they run consistently and securely across different computer systems.

Controlled access

Restrictions that ensure only approved users can access data, usually under strict rules and monitoring.

Cost recovery

Charging users or projects fees to cover the cost of running secure data services.

Cross-domain data

Data combined from different sectors (for example, health, education and employment) to answer broader research questions.

De-identification

The process of removing obvious personal details (like names or NHS numbers) from data to reduce the risk of identifying individuals.

Federated analysis

Sending analytical jobs (scripts, queries, workflows) to be executed remotely inside one or more TREs. Jobs can be sent from within a TRE or from a dedicated submission service.

Federation (of TREs)

Connecting multiple TREs so research can be carried out across them while each keeps control of its own data.

Governance

The policies, rules and oversight processes that ensure data is used legally, ethically and securely.

High-performance computing (HPC)

Powerful computing systems designed to handle very large or complex calculations quickly.

Interoperability

The ability of different systems or organisations to work together and share data smoothly.

ISO 27001

An international standard for managing information security risks.

NHS Data Security and Protection Toolkit (DSPT)

A UK framework organisations must follow to demonstrate safe handling of health and care data.

Output checking (or disclosure control)

A review process to make sure that research results leaving a TRE do not accidentally reveal sensitive information.

Public involvement and engagement (PIE)

Activities that involve members of the public in decisions about how sensitive data is used for research, to build trust and transparency.

Re-identification

When people could potentially be identified again by combining de-identified data with other information.

Relational database

An organised collection of data, where data are related to each other in a systematic manner so that they can be reorganised and accessed in different ways.

Research in the public benefit

Research intended to produce benefits for society, such as improving health, public services, or policy, rather than private profit.

SATRE (Standard Architecture for Trusted Research Environments)

A shared technical blueprint describing best practice for how TREs should be designed and operated.

Sensitive data

Information that could identify people, organisations, or confidential activities, such as health records, financial details, or personal identifiers.

Trusted Research Environment (TRE)

A highly secure digital space where approved researchers can safely access and analyse sensitive data without being able to download or copy it.

4 Introduction

This report is a snapshot of the UK's provision of digital infrastructure to support public research with sensitive data at the end of 2025. It follows on from the 2023 DARE UK landscape review, albeit with a tighter focus on sensitive data infrastructure and a redesigned survey.

Our aim was to create as rich a picture as we could of this part of the research landscape. As before, the primary focus of the report has been on infrastructure supporting publicly funded, rather than private, research use, often qualified further (especially with regards to the use of individual-level public data) as “research in the public benefit”.

Large, privately operated research infrastructures (those internal to pharmaceutical firms, for instance) were outside of our scope.

We draw out points of comparison between this review and the 2023 version where these are possible (see in particular Chapter 10: Landscape Trends).

4.1 Methodology

This review adopted a mixed-method, survey-based approach to collect and analyse information on the operations, governance and sustainability of Trusted Research Environments (TREs) across the United Kingdom. A structured online questionnaire was designed and advertised broadly to organisations and communities within the TRE ecosystem, including academic institutions, public sector bodies, private companies and third-sector organisations. The survey explored multiple dimensions of TRE activities, such as infrastructure capabilities, governance processes, funding mechanisms, sustainability planning and public involvement and engagement practices.

We used the following criterion to gate survey respondents:

Based on this definition of sensitive data:

“Sensitive data includes data which contains personally identifiable information such as names, addresses and identifying numbers. This can still be sensitive once it has been de-identified (has had all personal identifiable information removed) if there is potential for re-identification, particularly when used with other data. Commercial data such as retail information, business details, IP (intellectual property) and Copyright information or confidential product details may also be considered sensitive data.”

Does your research infrastructure/organisation process or provide sensitive data for research purposes?

A total of 63 organisations answered “yes” and went on to complete the survey, providing a robust and diverse dataset that captures perspectives from across the national TRE landscape.

Following the closure of the survey, all responses were compiled, cleaned and verified for completeness and accuracy. Quantitative data were analysed using descriptive statistical techniques to identify patterns, sectoral differences and emerging trends, while qualitative responses were reviewed through thematic analysis to draw out deeper insights into challenges, best practices and evolving priorities.

This mixed analytical approach provided a balanced understanding of both measurable performance indicators and the contextual factors shaping TRE operations. The resulting analysis offers a comprehensive overview of the current state of the TRE ecosystem in the UK, highlighting common strengths, areas for improvement and opportunities for future development and coordination across the ecosystem.

The survey ran between April and September 2025 and was advertised through a variety of channels including websites, newsletters, workshops and conferences, as well as by direct email.

Overall, the survey received responses from most of the large regional or national TRE services in the UK, including:

- 11 of 12 NHS national and regional Secure Data Environments in England
- All five members of the Scottish Safe Haven Network in Scotland
- The SAIL Databank as the national TRE in Wales
- The Northern Ireland Honest Broker Service in Northern Ireland
- UK-wide data research infrastructures such as the ONS Secure Research Service, UK Data Service, UK Biobank, OurFutureHealth and OpenSAFELY

Beyond these larger services, we received responses from around 40 smaller providers across the landscape. It is very difficult to gauge our coverage and the representativeness of this sample against the overall population of TREs and related services, principally because we do not have a good estimate for the size of the population. Anecdotally we are aware of significant TRE provision – for example, among UK universities – driven in part by a growing emphasis from research funders on trusted research and innovation methods. We feel it likely that a “long tail” of smaller institutional and departmental TRE services exists. Understanding how best to reach more of them in future surveys is one of our takeaways from this exercise.

5 Landscape overview

This section provides a general overview of the different types of organisations that make up the UK’s TRE landscape, outlining their distribution, sectoral representation and respective roles in supporting sensitive data research.

WHAT IS A TRUSTED RESEARCH ENVIRONMENT (TRE)?

A TRE is a highly secure computing environment where approved researchers can log in to analyse sensitive datasets to advance research for public benefit. The source data stays inside the TRE: anything researchers want to take out (like summary results, charts or tables) is checked to make sure it does not reveal information about any individual. TREs also keep records of who accessed what, and when, and operate under strict rules and oversight.

WHAT IS SENSITIVE DATA?

In this report, sensitive data includes information that could identify a person (directly or indirectly) or reveal something private or confidential. This can include social care and education information, health records, or detailed survey responses, for example. Even when obvious identifiers like names and addresses are removed, data can still be sensitive if there is a risk someone could be identified by combining it with other data sources. Some commercial or confidential business information can also be sensitive.

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5.1 Types of organisations

Overall, academic institutions and public sector organisations together account for more than three-quarters of respondents, highlighting their dominant role in the sensitive data research ecosystem. The remaining respondents are spread across third-sector organisations, private companies and other entities, reflecting the diversity of contributors to this landscape (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Breakdown of respondents by organisation type

ACADEMIC INSTITUTIONS

Academic institutions form the largest share of our respondents, making up 41% of the sample. As highlighted in previous national reviews, universities continue to be central to the UK’s research ecosystem, and this is equally true for research involving sensitive data. Many universities are not only engaged in research but also play a significant role in hosting and managing infrastructure to support TREs.

PUBLIC SECTOR ORGANISATIONS

Public sector organisations account for 36% of respondents. These include a diverse range of entities, such as health bodies, national agencies and government departments. Rather than breaking them down further, we focus on their shared role in supporting and regulating the sensitive data research landscape. Their significant representation highlights the ongoing reliance on publicly funded organisations in this domain.

THIRD-SECTOR ORGANISATIONS

Third-sector organisations such as charities, research institutes and non-profits make up 8% of the sample. While smaller in proportion, their contribution remains important, particularly where they fund or facilitate research addressing critical societal challenges, including health and social care.

PRIVATE SECTOR COMPANIES

Private sector companies represent 10% of the organisations surveyed. For this review, the focus was on companies directly providing infrastructure or platform-level services relevant to TREs. This excludes the wider set of private sector actors delivering tools, software, or consultancy services, though their role in the broader sensitive data ecosystem is well recognised.

OTHERS

The “Other” category, representing 5% of the sample, captures organisations that do not fit neatly into the categories above. This includes unique or finite projects and cross-sector initiatives without permanent institutional status. While smaller in number, they play valuable roles in shaping and piloting innovative approaches to sensitive data research.

5.2 Geographical distribution of research infrastructures across the UK

The geographical spread of research infrastructures across the UK highlights both regional strengths and the concentration of resources within certain areas. At the national level, all four nations of the UK – England, Scotland, Wales and Northern Ireland – are represented, reflecting the shared responsibility for advancing sensitive data research across the devolved administrations. Figure 2 shows the distribution of different types of organisation across the UK among respondents.

Figure 2. Distribution of organisation types across the UK

Out of 63 respondents, 10 reported being “multi-regional”, with sites in multiple locations across the UK. 40 were England-only, nine were Scotland-only, three were based exclusively in Northern Ireland and one was based solely in Wales. The pin map (Figure 3) shows the distribution of respondents across the UK.

Respondents for England were asked to report the English region in which they were based. The regional maps in Figure 4 contrast the reported locations of TREs and related organisations with the 2024 population figures for each area. Within England, the distribution is uneven, with London emerging as the dominant hub, accounting for the largest concentration of sites (17; 27%). This reflects the capital’s role as both a centre of academic excellence and a focal point for national health and government data initiatives. Other significant clusters are in the Northwest (7; 11%), the East of England (6; 10%) and Yorkshire and the Humber (6; 10%). These areas are home to leading universities and NHS infrastructures, reinforcing their position in national research networks. Regions such

as the West Midlands and Southwest with three respondents each (5%) show smaller but still meaningful contributions, often linked to specialised institutions or health data platforms.

This uneven distribution indicates a strong centralisation of research infrastructure in London and a handful of English regions, balanced by strategic nodes in Scotland, Wales and Northern Ireland.

Together, these hubs form a UK-wide network, though the concentration in certain regions raises important questions about equitable access to research resources and the potential for strengthening capacity in underrepresented areas.

Figure 3. Geographical distribution of survey respondents across the UK

TREs and TRE-related sites

Population (2024; m)

Powered by Bing. © Microsoft, Open Place, OpenStreetMap

Figure 4. Geographical concentration of TREs and TRE-related sites (left) and UK regional populations (right)

5.3 Inter-TRE collaboration

The collaboration and network map in Figure 5 visualises the geographical connections among TREs and related sensitive data infrastructure sites across the UK. It specifically illustrates how various TREs, data providers and platform providers interact within the wider UK data research ecosystem. Note that the map represents only those TREs that explicitly reported existing collaborative relationships in the survey.

Most reported connections were local, within the same city or small region, such as between universities and local NHS trusts. Beyond these, the map shows a number of broader, country-wide networks, including:

- The NHS Secure Data Environment Network in England
- The Scottish Safe Haven Network
- Service-platform links between TREs and the UK SeRP platform
- Hosting links between TREs and commercial providers
- Regional collaborative networks in the Thames valley and Yorkshire

Figure 5. Reported working links between TRE and TRE-related sites across the UK

5.4 Organisations and their roles

We asked respondents to choose up to three roles in which they saw themselves in the ecosystem. Subsequent questions were based on this choice of roles. We defined the roles as follows:

TRE SERVICE PROVIDER

Delivers the specialist services needed to support and operate a TRE, complementing the roles of data providers (who supply the data) and platform providers (who host the TRE infrastructure). Service providers typically handle data management, user support, governance processes, training and analytic services for research projects. They ensure that researchers not only have secure access to data but also the guidance, approvals and tools they need to use it responsibly and effectively.

TRE PLATFORM PROVIDER

Builds, operates and maintains the underlying infrastructure for the TRE. While the data provider supplies the data, the platform provider ensures the technical infrastructure and technical security controls are in place. Their responsibilities include managing secure logins and audit trails, and maintaining the security of the underlying hardware, virtualisation software and other infrastructure-level services.

DATA PROVIDER

Supplies datasets to a TRE. The provider owns and governs the data, ensuring it is high-quality, pseudonymised where necessary, and shared in line with legal, ethical and regulatory standards. They also work with TRE Service Providers (see above) to set conditions for access so researchers can only extract safe, aggregate results rather than individual-level data.

Respondents classified themselves as shown in Figure 6. Overall, around 55% of respondents operate in more than one role, with 32% performing all three roles simultaneously.

We structure the next three chapters around these sets of responses, looking first at TRE Service Providers.

ROLES AND OVERLAPS

Figure 6. Self-reported organisational roles within the landscape, and overlaps between them (counts; total 63)

6 TRE service providers

TRE Service Providers manage and operate TREs. They are perhaps what most people think of when they think of “a TRE”. TRE Service Providers provide data management, user support, governance processes, training and analytic services. In our definition, TRE Service Providers are researcher-facing, ensuring that researchers have secure access to data and the guidance, approvals and tools they need to use it responsibly and effectively.

To TRE Service Providers we asked questions on the user-base they support, the kinds of project they undertake, the data they work with and the analytical and research environments they provide. We asked about the governance and disclosure control processes they follow and their support for advanced capabilities including high-performance computing, support for artificial intelligence and machine learning, and inter-TRE federated analytics.

Figure 7 combines the cumulative counts of TRE Service Providers by year of instantiation from this survey and the 2023 survey, correcting for double entries and reviewing any TREs that have gone out of service. Our 2023 survey “extended sample” included a cohort of planned TREs due to come onstream between 2023 and 2025. These are now counted formally in the 2025 survey sample.

Overall, 48 of 63 respondents (76%) categorised themselves as TRE Service Providers.

Figure 7. Cumulative count of TRE service providers by year of instantiation. This chart combines results from both 2023 and 2025, correcting for double counting and TREs closing service

6.1 Users and projects

ACTIVE PROJECTS PER YEAR

The survey data highlights the wide variation in the number of active research projects supported by TREs each year, reflecting significant differences in institutional scale, infrastructure capacity and research focus (Figure 8).

Nearly half of TRE Service Providers operate on a scale supporting up to 25 active projects annually. A small number (9), mainly large public sector platforms, operate at a much higher scale, managing over 250 projects annually. By contrast, charity and private sector TREs appear to manage fewer projects overall, generally within the 0–50 range.

Figure 8. Numbers of research projects hosted annually by TRE Service Providers (counts; n=48)

We followed up with TRE Service Providers reporting “more than 500” projects to gauge a more accurate picture; responses were in the range 750-1,500.

Figure 9 charts the numbers of projects against the “age” of the TRE Service Provider (their reported number of years of operation). There is a slight but discernible trend that older TREs support more projects (the yellow and pink categories).

Overall, the estimated total number of active projects across our respondents falls in the range 4,726 to 8,811, with a median value of 6,769. As noted in the Introduction (Section 4.1) our coverage across major (national and regional) UK TRE providers is fairly comprehensive. While extrapolation is dangerous, we can take the median of 6,769 as a reasonable lower bound to the median number of active UK research projects using sensitive data in 2025.

Figure 9. Number of research projects hosted annually by TRE Service Providers relative to their “age”

CROSS-DOMAIN PROJECTS

The findings show (Figure 10) that for almost half of TREs, fewer than 10% of their projects involve cross-domain data. This suggests that, for many TREs, data access remains focused on well-defined subject areas – such as health, social care, or education – rather than spanning multiple sectors.

Around a quarter report that 10–30% of their work involves cross-domain integration, while a smaller group operate in a moderately cross-linked space with 31-60% of projects drawing from different data domains. Notably, nearly one in five TREs engage in high levels of cross-domain research, where most projects combine datasets from multiple sectors.

Taken together, the results indicate that while cross-domain data use is emerging, it is not yet widespread across the TRE landscape. The limited proportion of TREs working extensively across domains likely reflects the technical, governance and legal complexities of linking data from different custodians or policy areas. However, the presence of a growing minority engaging in multi-domain research suggests increasing capability and interest in this area, which could become a key feature of the TRE ecosystem as interoperability and data-sharing frameworks continue to mature.

Figure 10. Percentage numbers of cross-domain projects hosted annually by TRE Service Providers (counts; n=48)

Figure 11. Number of monthly active users reported by TRE Service Providers (counts; n=48)

MONTHLY USER RANGE

When compared with the annual project activity levels, the pattern of monthly user access highlights an important distinction between the number of projects a TRE supports and the intensity of ongoing engagement within the environment. While many TREs manage a modest number of projects each year, their monthly user figures suggest steady, active use, indicating that a smaller set of projects may involve multiple researchers or sustained, long-term analysis rather than short-term access.

Most academic TREs report between 11 and 50 users per month, showing a consistent flow of researchers working within secure environments throughout the year. A few larger academic platforms accommodate over 100 users monthly, aligning with institutions that also reported higher annual project counts. In the public sector, user activity is more widely distributed: some smaller departmental TREs host fewer than 10 users, while major national platforms engage over 500 users each month, reflecting their broader mandate and infrastructure capacity.

Figure 11 charts monthly user numbers among TRE Service Providers, and Figure 12 combines the service age, project and user numbers into a single visualisation.

Figure 12. Numbers of monthly users (outer ring) vs numbers of annual projects (middle ring) vs “age” of TRE Service providers (inner ring)

6.2 Data management and access

When asking about types of data we used the following categories.

Health data

Subdivided as:

- Primary care (secondary use of routine GP or community health data).
- Secondary care (secondary use of routine hospital data).
- Genomics (primary capture from detailed lab analyses of individual genomes).
- Clinical trials (health outcomes in the context of new treatments).
- Research cohort data (collected by research projects).

Administrative data

Subdivided as:

- Employment, welfare, social care and deprivation.
- Education (secondary use of data from schools).
- Justice (secondary use of routine criminal justice, courts and/or prisons data).
- Financial (secondary use of personal financial data, more often that of “legal persons” [firms] than “natural persons”).
- Surveys (detailed “microdata” from individual-level surveys).

“Smart” data

Subdivided as:

- Internet usage (secondary use of search history data).
- Social media (secondary use of social media data).
- Wearables (secondary use of wearable device data, including smart watch data).
- Mobile phone (secondary use of tracking or geographic data from mobile phones).

Commercial data

Subdivided as:

- Intellectual property (provided for particular research purposes, perhaps under non-disclosure agreements or other contractual means).
- Sales and retail (again, provided for particular research purposes, perhaps under non-disclosure agreements or other contractual means).

Defence or national security

(potentially data government-classified as SECRET or higher).

“Other” data

Here, classes of *personal* data (health, administrative, “smart”) could be either routinely collected data, used for research under GDPR “public benefit” permissions (with patient opt-out for health data), or data included as part of a research cohort and used under GDPR “consent” permissions.

TYPES OF DATA

The range of sensitive data managed and provided by TRE Service Providers reflects the diversity of research purposes they support and the broad policy areas they serve (Figure 13). Health-related data dominates across all sectors, particularly secondary care datasets, which are used by nearly nine in 10 public sector TREs and two-thirds of academic and private sector respondents. Primary care data is also widely managed, especially within public and academic TREs, highlighting the central role of routinely collected health information in UK research.

Figure 13. Number of TRE Service Providers providing research access to data of particular types (counts; n=48)

We note that, given the recognised challenges in accessing unconsented GP data for research [3], it is likely that many TREs reporting that they host GP data are referring to GP information linked and contained within consented research cohorts they manage.

Research cohort data and clinical trial datasets, both typically consented, are also common, particularly within academic environments. Over two-thirds of academic institutions reported managing cohort data, and nearly half handle clinical trials. This demonstrates the strong alignment between TREs and the research institutions generating or stewarding consent-based datasets. Genomic data, while less prevalent overall, features most prominently in academic settings, often linked to biobank and precision medicine initiatives.

Beyond health, social and administrative datasets form a substantial part of TRE activity. A significant proportion

manage employment, welfare and social care data, while smaller but notable numbers handle education, justice and financial data. These patterns suggest a growing emphasis on cross-sectoral research, particularly within public sector TREs that hold access to large, linked administrative datasets.

Less common are emerging and non-traditional data types such as wearables, mobile phone, internet usage and social media data, which appear only sporadically in the responses. Their limited representation likely reflects the complexities of consent, data ownership and governance associated with these sources. Similarly, only a few TREs reported handling defence, intellectual property, or commercial sales data, highlighting how such datasets remain highly restricted or project-specific.

ACCESS METHODS AND FORMATS

TREs support a broad range of data formats to meet diverse research needs (Figure 14), though most survey respondents continue to prioritise simplicity and accessibility.

The majority supply data as flat files such as CSV or Excel, reflecting a strong preference for formats that are easy to handle, integrate and audit within secure environments, and three-fifths provide relational database extracts.

Figure 14. Working data formats supported by TRE Service Providers (counts; n=48)

Semi-structured formats like JSON or XML are supported by around a third of TREs, while more complex structured formats like Apache Parquet are supported by 35%. Image data such as DICOM or GeoTIFF files crucial in specialised research domains such as geospatial and biomedical studies are provided by nearly half of respondents. Around a fifth reported offering GIS data, and one in 10 provided API-based access.

A sixth selected “Other,” with qualitative responses pointing to custom or platform-specific data provisioning methods aligned with their internal architectures and platform tooling.

DATA LINKAGE

Most TREs offer some form of data linkage service. We asked about linkage using the five principal indices in the ONS Reference Data Management Framework². Among respondents, the most common indices for data linkage are addresses and demographic identifiers, forming the backbone of linkage activity in both academic and public sector environments (Figure 15). Business identifiers, classifications and precise geolocation data are used far less frequently, and mainly in specialist contexts.

Among those TREs which offer data linkage services (40; 83%), methods are dominated by deterministic approaches based on unique identifiers, often complemented by rule-based and probabilistic techniques for more complex or incomplete datasets. Manual review remains a supplementary method, while machine learning-based linkage is emerging but not yet widely adopted (Figure 16).

Figure 15. Index types used by TREs in data linkage by number of TREs (counts; n=48)

Figure 16. Data linkage methods in use by TRE Service Providers (counts and proportions; n=48)

²See <https://www.ons.gov.uk/aboutus/whatwedo/programmesandprojects/referencedatamanagementframework>

6.3 Governance processes

INFORMATION GOVERNANCE SERVICES

Most TREs provide information governance services as part of their overall offering, extending beyond infrastructure management to include functions such as project approval, user accreditation and output checking. Across all respondents, around 85% reported that they deliver these governance components directly within their TRE service.

Governance services are most consistent in the public and third sectors, where all respondents indicated that they are integrated into their operational model. This reflects the strong regulatory obligations and accountability frameworks under which these organisations typically operate. Academic institutions also show a high level of in-house governance provision, with around three-quarters offering these services, often through dedicated data access or research governance teams.

In contrast, the private sector presents a more mixed picture: only half of respondents reported providing governance functions as part of their TRE service. This variation may reflect differing business models.

OUTPUT CHECKING

Most TREs enforce technical controls that prevent researchers from freely downloading data. Instead, any results intended for export must be placed in an internal “airlock,” where they undergo review to ensure that analytical outputs do not compromise individual privacy. This is called output checking or disclosure control.

Of the TREs surveyed, 88% reported that disclosure control checks are carried out independently by the TRE, rather than by the research teams, prior to any data export. A further 6% rely on members of the research team – often the project’s principal investigator – to conduct these checks. 2% of the TREs surveyed reported “Other”, and a further 4% gave no answer.

Full manual review remains the dominant method of output checking across the TRE landscape (Figure 17). 69% of all respondents indicated that outputs are reviewed by a data governance or disclosure control team before release, ensuring that any information leaving the secure environment is compliant with confidentiality and data protection requirements. This strong reliance on human oversight reflects the continued importance of professional judgment in assessing disclosure risk, particularly for sensitive datasets.

Semi-automated tools are used by a modest proportion of TREs (19%). These tools help flag potential disclosure risks or policy breaches but are generally used to support, rather than replace, independent human review.

No respondents reported using fully automated systems, highlighting that complete automation is not currently a feature of TRE governance. The preference for manual and semi-automated approaches likely stems from the complexity and contextual nature of disclosure control, which often requires case-by-case interpretation.

Where TREs were not using (semi-)automated software and tools (n=35; 74%), half were currently developing or evaluating potential approaches; over a third were not proceeding at this stage; and around one in 10 were yet to consider semi-automated tooling support.

Of the TREs currently using semi-automated tools or hybrid approaches (n=15; 32%), four reported using the DARE UK-funded SACRO (Semi-Automated Checking of Research Outputs) toolset³. The remainder were using bespoke or platform-proprietary approaches.

Figure 17. Output checking process in place at TRE Service Providers

³SACRO (Semi-Automated Checking of Research Outputs) is a suite of tools designed to help researchers assess the privacy disclosure risks of their outputs, including tables, plots, statistical models and trained machine learning models.

6.4 Analytical tools and compute features

STANDARD ANALYTICAL TOOLS

Python and R dominate as the primary analytical tools across all TREs, reflecting their flexibility, open-source nature and wide adoption within the research community (Figure 18). Among proprietary tools, Stata is the most common, followed by SPSS and SAS. These packages remain particularly prominent in academic and public sector TREs, where long-established research programmes continue to rely on these traditional statistical environments for consistency and comparability of outputs. Business intelligence (BI) tools such as Tableau or Power BI are available in a smaller number of TREs, mainly within the academic and public sectors, supporting visualisation and interactive reporting needs.

Nearly half of TREs reported providing access to “other” analytical tools, and of these nearly half again provide the flexibility for users either to request additional tools or deploy their own through “bring your own container” services, equating to a fifth of all TRE Service Providers.

Figure 18. Availability of analytical software tools in TREs (counts; n=48)

Figure 19. Analytical tooling preferences across data domains

WORKFLOW TOOLS

Around a fifth of TREs currently provide researchers with access to workflow management systems. Among those that do provide access, most offer workflow systems available within their providers’ proprietary environments. A small number of TREs mentioned Nextflow, Apache Airflow and Snakemake.

MACHINE LEARNING TOOLS

A clear majority of TRE Service Providers (69%) now offer tools which support the training of artificial intelligence and machine learning models within their researcher environments (Figure 20). Most of the established tools were represented across the sample, with no particular winner. Of those TREs who chose “Other”, over half indicated that users could request almost any software be installed within their project environments.

Figure 20. AI/ML tooling supported by TREs (counts; n=48)

CODE SHARING

All of the TREs that responded to the question (43 of 48) confirmed that they enable researchers to share code between themselves within the same project (Figure 21, left). The most common mechanism is through shared folders within secure workspaces which allow project team members to access and modify code collectively. Almost half also use version control systems such as GitLab, reflecting a growing adoption of structured, auditable code management practices that support reproducibility and good software governance. Almost two-fifths offer sharing through collaborative platforms such as Jupyter Hub or R Studio Server.

When asked “Does your TRE provide a service for sharing code between users on different projects?” a slightly different picture emerges (Figure 21 right). Here, nearly two-fifths of TREs do not allow code sharing between projects at all, and of those that do, manual code transfer is the favoured mechanism. More automated mechanisms, such as version control, are noticeably less prevalent (we did not offer the response “shared folders” in this question, as this is regarded as bad practice).

Figure 21. Methods provided by TREs to share analysis code between users on the same project (left) in comparison to users on different projects (right)

SHARED COMPUTING SYSTEMS

Half of TRE Service Providers provide users with the capability to submit computational jobs to non-desktop or high-performance compute (HPC) resources, against a small majority who do not (11% gave no response).

As shown in Figure 22, among those offering this capability the most supported system is **SLURM** (used by eight TREs, or 44% of those offering the capability), a well-established job scheduler widely adopted in research computing environments. A smaller number support the Databricks execution service.

We asked explicitly about the [Global Alliance for Genomics and Health \(GA4GH\) standards Workflow Execution Service \(WES\)](#) and [Task Execution Service \(TES\)](#). TES is in use in two TREs and WES in only one, as are all other job management services mentioned in narrative responses to the category "Other". We observe that these are small numbers, and drawing any conclusions is unsafe.

These results overall suggest that, while advanced compute capability is available in a significant subset of TREs, the landscape remains highly heterogeneous. This perhaps reflects differences in infrastructure maturity, hosting models and the complexity of supported research workloads.

CONTAINER SUPPORT

More than half of TRE Service Providers support the use of containerisation technologies for user workloads (Figure 23).

Among those offering this functionality, Docker is by far the most widely supported technology, used by nearly all respondents that allow containerisation. This indicates its position as the de facto standard across both academic and government research infrastructures.

Singularity is available in about a third of academic TREs but is less prevalent overall, likely due to its more specialised use in high-performance computing contexts. A small number of TREs reported using Podman or other container tools such as Kata, with only isolated mentions, suggesting experimentation with alternative solutions focused on security or specific infrastructure configurations.

Figure 22. Tools offered by TRE Service Providers to support execution of jobs on non-desktop compute systems (n=18)

Figure 23. Container and container orchestration technologies supported by TRE Service Providers (n=28)

SOFTWARE INSTALLATION AND DEPENDENCY MANAGEMENT

Most TREs (80%) support requests for new software installations, demonstrating a strong commitment to providing researchers with flexible and adaptable analytical environments (Figure 24).

Figure 24. Mechanisms offered to users by TRE Service Providers for software installation

The most common method is via external requests to TRE support teams where installations are managed centrally to maintain compliance with security and governance controls. "Bring Your Own Code" options, where researchers can upload and run their own software or scripts, are supported by 21 TREs, offering additional flexibility for bespoke analysis while maintaining oversight through

sandboxing or containerisation. Just over a quarter also allow self-service installation within the TRE platform, giving users limited internal access to install approved software themselves – an approach more typical of technically mature or cloud-based environments. A small number of respondents allow the installation of new analysis packages (e.g. for Python or R), but not of general software.

6.5 Federated analytics and inter-TRE capabilities

We asked Service Providers, “At what stage of development is the TRE in providing federated analysis capabilities?”, with the following options:

- Planning phase (designing an architecture for federated analysis)
- Partial implementation (federated analysis trialled, or in place with some, but not all, systems)
- Federated analysis (fully operational)

The results are graphed in Figure 25.

Of the TRE Service Providers who responded, most remain in the early or experimental stages of enabling federated analysis (see the glossary in Chapter 3). There was no dominant approach reported by those in the early, experimental stages. Only two TREs reported having fully operational federated analysis capabilities, showing that large-scale interoperability remains rare.

Among the Service Providers exploring federated analytics, some have begun integrating automated job submission layers that validate incoming workflows and metadata before execution, while others rely on manual review and scheduling to ensure compliance with security and provenance requirements. In many cases, external ingress is only permitted from trusted institutional or platform partners, with additional safeguards such as encryption, access control and sandboxing to prevent unauthorised interaction.

Challenges to providing federated analytics noted by Service Providers include: heterogeneity in infrastructure and system configurations across TREs; constraints around containerisation, particularly the need for elevated privileges to run containers securely; data and system variability; documentation gaps; and the reproducibility of research workflows, noting that standardisation efforts will take time to mature.

Figure 25. Status of provision of federated analytics across TRE Service Providers

6.6 Underpinning infrastructure

This section provides an overview of the technical foundations that underpin the operation of TREs across the UK. It examines how TREs are hosted and supported, the features and tools they provide to users, and the rationale behind key infrastructure choices.

PLATFORM CHOICE

We asked Service Providers, “Who provides the platform for your TRE?”, with multiple options to be chosen from:

- On-premises (installed and managed by the organisation)
- Specialist TRE platform provider (e.g. UKSeRP, ARO, Aridhia)
- General purpose external cloud platform provider (e.g. AWS, Azure, Google Cloud)

Figure 26 shows the results, and Figure 27 breaks down the choices of external cloud provider for the 24 TREs who reported external cloud use.

Figure 26. Infrastructure platforms reported by TRE Service Providers (n=48)

Figure 27. Choice of external cloud provider reported by those TREs reporting “General purpose external cloud platform provider” (n=24)

TRE PLATFORM SOFTWARE

We asked Service Providers about the kind of software their TRE infrastructure is built from, whether third-party open-source (e.g. Linux, Docker, PostgreSQL), proprietary (e.g. Microsoft Windows, Oracle Database, Snowflake, Databricks), cloud-specific (e.g. AWS Lambda, Microsoft Azure Functions), or custom-built solutions. Respondents could select as many as applied, and the results are shown in Figure 28.

This paints a fairly heterogeneous picture, with no clear trends. Over a third of Service Providers still writing a lot of their own custom software indicates that TRE provision is not yet a turn-key business. Nearly half of TRE infrastructure being built using cloud-specific technologies may suggest that portability or future migration to other platforms could be a sizeable challenge.

Figure 29 shows responses to the question, "Who develops and supports the infrastructure software for your TRE?" These offer a corollary to the technologies question; a large majority of TRE Service Providers rely at least in part on an in-house team to maintain the software infrastructure.

Figure 28. Responses from TRE Service Providers to the question "What types of software technologies are used to build the TRE?" (counts; n=48)

- In-house team
- In-house + external
- In-house + platform
- TRE platform provider
- External partners or consultants

Figure 29. Responses from TRE Service Providers to the question "Who develops and supports the infrastructure software for your TRE?" (n=48)

IDENTITY MANAGEMENT SYSTEMS

Variation in identity management systems is a particular concern for interoperability between TREs, for instance to enable federated analytics. We asked Service Providers which systems their TREs supported (Figure 30).

Identity management within TREs is anchored in established enterprise directory services, with 64% of respondents using Microsoft's Active Directory. This encompasses both on-premises and cloud-based use; 9% of respondents mentioned the "cloud flavour" Entra ID explicitly in narrative answers.

LDAP is supported by just over a quarter of TREs, while around a fifth employ Keycloak, an open-source identity and access management solution that supports modern authentication protocols such as OpenID Connect and SAML.

Figure 30. Identity management systems in use by TRE Service Providers (counts; n=48)

TRE HARDWARE RESOURCES

In terms of hardware resources available within TREs for computational tasks, the vast majority of respondents offer general-purpose desktop computing, ensuring baseline accessibility for most research needs (Figure 31). More advanced capabilities are also well represented, with over two-thirds providing GPU-enabled systems to support data-intensive workloads such as machine learning, and half hosting HPC clusters for large-scale simulations or analytics. This distribution suggests that while almost all TREs meet general computing requirements, a significant proportion are equipped for more specialised, high-capacity processing demands.

Figure 31. Computing capabilities available within TREs (counts; n=48)

7 TRE platform providers

We characterise Platform Providers as those organisations which build, operate and maintain the underlying hardware, software and networking infrastructure for a TRE. Platform Providers ensure the required technical infrastructure and security controls are in place and maintained and monitored appropriately. In particular, Platform Providers are responsible for the maintenance regime for the underlying hardware, virtualisation software and other infrastructure-level services.

7.1 Service models and infrastructure hosting

We asked, "What types of service does your platform offer?", with the following choices:

- Fully managed service (TRE setup and operation are fully managed by you as Platform Provider)
- Partially managed service (TRE setup and certain aspects are managed by you as Platform Provider, while others are managed by the TRE Service Provider)
- Self-managed service (TRE setup is managed by you as Platform Provider, but operation is principally managed by the TRE Service Provider)
- Other

Figure 32 graphs the responses. The majority of Platform Providers operate on a fully managed service model, where both setup and operation are entirely handled by the provider. This may be correlated with the fact that four-fifths of Platform Providers also operate as Service Providers. No respondents reported self-managed services, again perhaps highlighting the strong overlap between the platform and service roles.

Figure 32. Services types offered by TRE Platform Providers (counts; n=28)

Overall, 28 of 63 (45%) respondents categorised themselves as TRE Platform Providers. Additionally, 82% of Platform Providers also categorised themselves as Service Providers.

7.2 Hosting strategy and rationale

To understand the adoption of public cloud services in TRE platforms, we asked, “Where is your infrastructure primarily hosted?”, with respondents able to select all options that applied. Figure 33 charts the results.

A clear three-quarters of Platform Providers make use of public cloud services in their offerings. Among the “big three” public cloud services, there is a fairly even 50:50 split between Amazon Web Services and Microsoft Azure, with none of our respondents reporting use of Google Cloud Platform. Figure 34 shows a breakdown of infrastructure hosting choices for Platform Providers by sector. In terms of the reported rationales for particular hosting choices, Figure 35 indicates that security, scalability and flexibility are

the most influential factors shaping decisions among Platform Providers. Security was cited by three-quarters of respondents, closely followed by scalability. Two-thirds cited flexibility. Taken together, these choices may highlight the importance of platforms being able to adapt to evolving research demands while maintaining data security.

Cost-effectiveness, performance and available skillsets were also significant considerations among more than half of respondents. The emphasis on existing skillsets suggests a pragmatic approach to technology adoption – organisations are more likely to choose hosting solutions aligned with their in-house expertise, reducing dependence on external support or retraining.

Figure 33. Infrastructure hosting choices reported by Platform Providers (n=28)

Figure 34. Platform Providers use of on-prem or public cloud hosting by sector (counts; n=28)

Figure 35. Responses by TRE Platform Providers to the question “What are the primary reasons for choosing your current hosting solution?”

8 TRE data providers

We defined the role of “TRE Data Provider” as an organisation that supplies datasets to a TRE. The provider owns and governs the data, ensuring it is high-quality, pseudonymised where necessary and shared in line with legal, ethical and regulatory standards.

The Data Provider role is often, but by no means always, combined with that of TRE Service Provider. In our survey, 40 organisations reported the role of Data Provider, of which just over a quarter (n=11) reported that role exclusively. The other 29 combined the roles of Data Provider and Service Provider. We highlight this division in the results below.

Our questions to Data Providers covered the subject matter and scope of the data they provide for researchers, technical matters such as delivery formats and transport mechanisms, and data linkage.

8.1 Types of data

Figure 36 shows answers to the question, "Which of the following types of data do you provide?". The list of choices was the same as presented to TRE Service Providers in Chapter 6.

In this and subsequent figures in this chapter we split respondents into "Pure Data Providers" (those reporting the single role of TRE Data Provider, labelled "Pure DPs") and those combining the roles of Data Provider and Service Provider ("DP+SPs"). The percentage figures for each category are the combined numbers out of the total 40 organisations reporting the Data Provider role.

Figure 36. Types of data provided for research by "pure" data providers and by organisations combining the roles of TRE data provider and service provider (labelled "DP+SPs" here and in subsequent figures in this chapter) (counts; n=40)

8.2 Scope and scale of datasets

Figure 37 shows the reported scale of datasets provided for research, whether local (e.g. town or city-scale), regional (e.g. county or region), devolved-national (England, Northern Ireland, Scotland, Wales) or UK-national.

In terms of scope, we asked providers to report on the effective legal basis by which they provide sensitive data. This included consented research cohorts, other consented cohorts (e.g. longitudinal studies), or unconsented cohorts, typically for research for public benefit (Figure 38). Where this was left blank (in three cases) we label it as "other". This arose typically in organisations who provide non-sensitive data (e.g. environmental data) to TREs for onward linkage with sensitive data.

Figure 39 graphs the types of access restriction placed on datasets by data providers after releasing data for research ("What kind of data access do you grant end-users after distribution?"). The only response allowing full dataset access was for access to non-sensitive environmental data; all other providers apply a mix of "safe data" constraints in addition to onward usage in TREs.

Figure 37. Data providers reporting their provision of datasets at local, regional or national scales (counts; n=40)

Figure 38. The scope of datasets provided for research (counts; n=40)

Figure 39. Types of restriction placed on dataset access by data providers (counts; n=40)

8.3 Data formats and delivery mechanisms

In terms of technical mechanisms, Figure 40 charts the "delivery formats" reported by Data Providers.

We asked, "Which of the following formats do you use to supply data for research purposes?", with options selectable from the following list:

- Simply structured flat files, e.g. CSV or Excel
- Relational database extracts, e.g. "SQL dump"
- Semi-structured flat files, e.g. JSON or XML
- Complex structured flat files, e.g. Apache Parquet, NetCDF, HDF4/5
- Image data, e.g. TIFF, GeoTIFF, DICOM
- GIS data
- By API access, e.g. GraphQL, custom RESTful APIs
- As real-time data e.g. live feeds

A catch-all category of "other" was reported by eight respondents, with narrative responses which enabled us to disambiguate into two further explicit categories: statistical data formats (e.g. bundled data/metadata in SPSS or Stata formats); and "omics" data, notably genomic data formats.

We also asked, "Which of the following mechanisms do you commonly use to deliver data for research purposes?", with options being: direct download from websites; file transfer (FTP, STFP); as online database e.g. by query language interface; via API access e.g. GraphQL, custom RESTful APIs; or by email. There were also 17 "other" responses, of which 16 gave a narrative answer which can be coded as, "by delivery into our local, or a close partner, TRE analytics environment".

Figure 40. Data delivery formats reported by data providers (counts; n=40)

Figure 41 charts the answers, including the narratives coded as “Directly into TRE”. One interesting point to note is that four of the 11 “Pure Data Providers” reported a “direct to TRE” delivery mechanism, perhaps suggesting close but separate working relationships with partner TREs.

The popularity of established file transfer tools such as ftp is underlined by the number of respondents who also reported using managed file transfer (MFT) services to move data (a technology that also encompasses the https protocol). 73% of Pure Data Providers and 70% of “DP+SPs” use MFT.

Figure 41. Delivery mechanisms reported by data providers (counts; n=40)

8.4 Data linkage

We asked data providers, “Which types of data linkage are most requested by researchers?”. The answers are graphed in Figure 42.

An interesting feature is that nearly half of the Pure Data Providers (five of 11) receive no requests for linked data, perhaps indicating that they specialise exclusively in one kind of data.

The “demographics” class covers linkage by individual people’s identifiers, including health-specific ones such as NHS number or Scotland’s community health index (CHI). “Addresses”, which can include postcodes or universal property reference numbers (UPRNs) are distinguished from “locations”, which are typically latitude/longitude pairs or other general geospatial indexes.

Figure 42. Types of data linkage requested by researchers of data providers. As noted earlier, the five categories “locations”, “classifications”, “businesses”, “demographics” and “addresses” are the five principal linkage indexes in the ONS Reference Data Management Framework (counts; n=40)

9 Standards and accreditation

Standards, accreditation and structured data management practices are increasingly central to how the TRE ecosystem maintains trust, quality and compliance. There are a several recognised frameworks with varying degrees of uptake across the TRE ecosystem as indicated in Figure 43 (see next page), with the most common among respondents being the NHS Data Security and Protection Toolkit (DSPT).

More general information and cyber security certifications such as ISO 27001, Cyber Essentials and Cyber Essentials+ are very well represented amongst respondents, as would be expected given the nature of the data across the TRE ecosystem.

Around 40% of respondents indicated plans to seek new or additional accreditations within the next year, reflecting ongoing efforts to strengthen assurance and demonstrate adherence to recognised frameworks.

Figure 43. Accreditation schemes and standards in use across the TRE ecosystem (counts; n=63)

Considering differences across sectors (Figure 43), ISO 27001 and the NHS DSPT are consistently the most prevalent across respondents, though within public sector respondents the NHS DSPT holds a clear majority, likely a result of simply a higher demand for health data from respondents and thus a greater proportion complying with accreditation standards aligned with handling health data safely and securely. Looking deeper into 'Other' accreditation standards as self-reported by respondents, these mostly refer to the evolving accreditation framework under development by the Department for Health and Social Care (DHSC) as part of its Data for Research and Development Programme, which brings together the network of NHS England Secure Data Environments.

Figure 44. Variations of accreditation and standards use by sector in the TRE ecosystem

With regard to pursuing or maintaining standards in the year ahead, over a quarter of respondents indicated a desire to do so, targeted primarily at securing ISO 27001 certification (7; 29%) with a few aiming for DEA 2017 (4; 17%) accreditation.

Respondents were also asked about their awareness of informal specifications (e.g. self-evaluated) or good practice frameworks, including the [Standard Architecture for Trusted Research Environments \(SATRE\)](#) specification, [FAIR data principles](#) (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) and Research Objects for data and metadata

packaging. Awareness of SATRE is high, with a large majority of respondents indicating familiarity (52; 84%) and close to half (28; 45%) indicating they have evaluated their TRE against the specification.

The FAIR principles are almost ubiquitous across respondents (59; 95%), with more than two thirds indicating active implementation in their infrastructures (42; 68%). However, adoption of Research Objects, such as [RO-Crates](#) for data and metadata packaging, remains limited (13; 21%), and of those most respondents reporting that this is still under development or applied only on request.

When considering how long respondents have provisioned services in the TRE ecosystem in comparison to the accreditation frameworks secured, a reasonable assumption would be that the longer respondents have operated within the TRE ecosystem, the more certifications they have managed to secure over that time (Figure 45). This assumption holds true at the ends of the time range (1-5 years and more than 10 years), but

interestingly we see a greater overall number of accreditations in the “1-5 years” as compared to the “6-10 years” time ranges. This perhaps reiterates that the TRE ecosystem has evolved significantly over the last few years with new organisations joining a set of established incumbents. Overall, it is clear that the TRE ecosystem will continue to see robust, credible accreditation to recognised standards as central to it maintaining trust, quality and compliance.

Figure 45. Adoption of accreditation and other standards by age of infrastructure (counts; n=63)

10 Sustainability and funding

Our questions to respondents covered the sources of funding, annual budget scale, the services they charge for and the models or mechanisms through which they receive or generate funding, alongside estimated proportions of the fixed and staff components thereof.

10.1 Funding sources

The TRE ecosystem relies on a diverse mix of funding sources, with public grants emerging as the most common form of support, as reported by around two-thirds of respondents. This could include income to support TRE activity as a component of a research grant for a specific data analysis project, or a research grant obtained purely to support the TRE infrastructure. Income from this source is especially strong among academic institutions (38%), where grant funding remains essential for sustaining infrastructure, governance and research activity (Figure 46).

This trend holds across all sectors where public grants represent the largest share of funding sources with the exception, unsurprisingly, of private sector companies, where public grants are less relevant than private investment and internal revenue sources (internal revenue

includes fees in “pay-as-you-go” or “top-slice” models of operation). Research institutions also play a major role, contributing to funding in 45% of respondents, often through institutional investment, staffing and maintenance. Charity and third-sector funding support are a smaller but important subset of the TRE ecosystem (around 26% overall), particularly for those involved in social or health-related research.

Figure 47 shows the numbers of organisations reporting “primary alignment” with the UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) research councils⁴ and other sources of funding. This question was deliberately unspecific, allowing organisations to indicate multiple choices. The answers offer an indication of the most common sources of funding for organisations operating in the TRE space.

Figure 46. Principal sources of funding by sector (share)

⁴See <https://www.ukri.org/councils>

Figure 47. Numbers of organisations reporting significant funding alignment with particular Research Councils. For organisation reporting “other”, we include a coding of narrative answers highlighting additional sources of funding (counts; n=63)

Zooming into the research and innovation funding landscape, specifically UKRI as the largest funder of research in the UK, there are several noticeable comparisons with the previous landscape review (acknowledging that the questions posed were slightly different between reviews and thus any inferences should be considered carefully):

- The Medical Research Council (MRC) and Economic and Social Research Council (ESRC) continue to represent the primary research areas within UKRI’s remit that sensitive data research infrastructures are aligned with, at 55% and 34% respectively. This echoes the previous landscape review, in which both councils featured prominently.
- Innovate UK has shown an increased footprint in this review, with almost 25% of respondents indicating this as their primary research council alignment. This is perhaps driven by an increasing interest from private sector companies in participating in the TRE ecosystem.

- Respondents indicating their primary alignment outside of UKRI, indicated by “Other” at 32%, can be grouped loosely into three categories: Government departments (e.g. Department for Science, Innovation and Technology, DHSC), devolved administrations (e.g. Welsh Government) and other large research funders (e.g. National Institute for Health and Care Research (NIHR), Wellcome Trust, Cancer Research UK). It should be noted that this category is still dominated by a strong bias towards health sciences, with more than 50% of organisations in this category with a clear health research mandate.
- All other research councils have remained largely stable, with no notable shifts as compared to the previous review.

In future surveys, greater exploration of research council funding via research project cost recovery versus purely infrastructure funding may be helpful.

10.2 Funding models

We defined three kinds of funding model around which we based our questions:

- CORE FUNDING**
 “You receive block grants or funds to cover essential and operational costs”.
- COST RECOVERY MECHANISM**
 “You recoup costs associated with providing specific services, e.g. by user-grant top-slicing or explicit service charges.”
- PROJECT-SPECIFIC FUNDING**
 “You seek funds to support particular development projects/ initiatives), e.g. by direct grant applications.”

Interestingly, there are no significant differences across sectors in terms of the mix of funding models. Figure 48 shows that across all sectors, core funding provides a significant proportion of funding in absolute terms, pointing towards a reliance on this model to provide a stable foundation to cover essential infrastructure, staffing and governance costs.

Cost recovery mechanisms are also widely used, with approximately 61% of respondents employing them to sustain operations. However, this appears to be more supplementary to core funding for the majority of respondents, rather than the primary funding model. Fixed user fees or grant top-slicing (where a small percentage charge is added to research grants) are the dominant approaches used by respondents to charge for a heterogenous set of services, as outlined in Figure 49 and Figure 50. Cost recovery has become an increasingly important strategy for achieving financial sustainability and ensuring that the cost of secure data management is equitably shared among users and funders.

Core (or block) funding remains the most common mechanism supporting TRE operations across all sectors, reported by about 71% of respondents. This is only marginally ahead of project-specific funding reported by 69% of respondents, and followed closely behind by cost-recovery mechanisms at 58%. Similar to funding sources, these figures indicate a diverse mix of funding models across the TRE ecosystem.

Figure 48. Funding models in use by TRE-related organisations across sectors

Figure 49. Models for services charged under cost recovery (counts; n=37)

Figure 50. For organisations reporting cost-recovery as a funding model, the numbers of those charging for given services (counts; n=37)

Project-specific funding is obtained through targeted grants or contracts to deliver defined initiatives. Project-specific funding represents another major source of financial support, used by about 70% of all respondents. It is particularly important for academic institutions and charity/ third sector organisations, where there is a greater reliance to fund new capabilities, collaborations and technical innovation through grants or contracts.

Public sector organisations also report significant use of project-based funding, primarily to develop new analytical tools or support cross-agency data programmes. Among private sector companies, this funding often comes through partnerships or co-funded initiatives. Although more variable than core funding, project-specific support plays a key role in driving growth, modernisation and interoperability across the TRE ecosystem, helping organisations remain adaptive in a rapidly evolving research landscape.

10.3 Funding scale

Given the perceived sensitivity around disclosing financial information, a total of 42 (66%) respondents reported annual budget figures in this review. Alongside a mix of funding sources, and likely as a result thereof, the TRE ecosystem boasts a relatively wide spread of annual funding. The annual budgets reported by respondents show a max/min range of

£20M/£20k per annum and a median of £1.0M per annum (Figure 51). Respondents reporting figures at the top end of the scale are all multi-site or multi-organisational, with major regional or national scope and reach. Staff account for more than half of annual costs in nearly two-thirds of respondents (63%) (Figure 52).

Figure 51. Annual operating budget (£M) for TRE-related organisations reporting (n=42)

Figure 52. Count of responses to the question "What fraction [of the infrastructure's total budget] is channelled towards human resources (operators, developers, support staff)?"

In terms of annual budget relative to the amount of time organisations have been provisioning services, the general expectation might be that the longer an organisation has been around, the larger its budget footprint. However, this is not the case in the TRE ecosystem. Figure 53 indicates a mixed bag in this regard and speaks to the journey that the TRE ecosystem in the UK has been on for several years now, typified by significant growth and change. Accordingly, investments at various scales exist for less than five years for almost half of respondents (46%).

Interestingly, there is a clear divide between 'new' organisations (less than five years old) within the TRE ecosystem and more 'mature' organisations (more than 10 years old), with only 8% of respondents between six and 10 years old.

Figure 53. Annual budget vs organisational "age", by sector

10.4 Long-term sustainability strategies

Organisations in the TRE ecosystem are pursuing a range of strategies to ensure their long-term sustainability, with several clear trends emerging across sectors (Figure 54).

We asked respondents to select from a list of options and offered an open-ended “other” category. We were able to code these narrative answers to provide additional information. All in all, most organisations use a number of strategic approaches to seek long-term sustainability.

Figure 54. Long-term sustainability strategies for research infrastructures. For organisation reporting “other”, we include a coding of narrative answers highlighting additional strategies reported (counts; n=63)

11 Public involvement and engagement

Here we explore how TREs involve the public in shaping governance, ensuring transparency and maintaining confidence in the use of sensitive data for research.

11.1 Importance of PIE

Public involvement and engagement (PIE) continue to be recognised as a cornerstone of trust and sustainability within the TRE ecosystem. The importance of involving the public as active partners in shaping governance, transparency and ethical standards is evident, with more than half of respondents engaging with the public on a monthly or quarterly basis, and a minority engaging only rarely (Figure 55). This regular engagement is maintained through ongoing communication channels or scheduled events, and to accompany specific projects or policy developments.

Figure 55. Reported frequency of public engagement by research infrastructures (n=63)

11.2 PIE methods and effectiveness

The results show that respondents undertake a wide range of PIE activities, employing a diverse set of methods to involve and engage the public (Figure 56). These activities work to build understanding, transparency and legitimacy around the use of sensitive data for research.

Workshops are the most common method of engaging and involving the public, reported by more than two thirds of respondents, serving

as interactive spaces for dialogue and feedback on data access and governance. Nevertheless, there was a broad spread of existing PIE activities across TREs, with community outreach also widely adopted (just over half of respondents), aimed at raising awareness, addressing public concerns and demonstrating the wider societal value of their work. Public consultations alongside surveys and polls also both feature prominently with around half of respondents.

Figure 56. Public involvement and engagement methods reported by research infrastructure organisations (n=63)

Figure 57. Mechanisms to involve public influence in decision making (n=63)

Figure 58. Main challenges reported by research infrastructures in engaging and involving the public. (n=63)

A little under half of respondents reported including members of the public on information governance panels to ensure that decisions about data use and project approvals reflect broader public values. When it comes to involvement in decision-making, the dominant approach is inclusion of public representatives on committees, with almost two thirds of respondents indicating this is an approach they take (Figure 57).

Figure 58 charts the main challenges to PIE cited by respondents, with limited resources being by far the largest. In the "Other" category, four respondents highlighted limited public understanding of the use of health data in particular in research.

11.3 PIE funding

Respondents allocate varying proportions of their total funding to PIE, with most reporting only modest or ad hoc investments (Figure 59). A third of respondents indicated that their PIE funding is not fixed, but determined on a project-by-project basis, reflecting flexible or demand-driven spending.

Among those assigning a specific proportion of funding to PIE, this was generally between one and five per cent of their total budgets. This may suggest that engagement activities are supported as part of broader operational or research funding, rather than as a standalone line item, or that they are being carried out infrequently and/or at relatively small scales.

A smaller group invests slightly more, typically between six and 15%, often corresponding to larger academic or public sector TREs with structured engagement strategies. Only a few reported allocating more than 15% of their funding to PIE.

As shown in Figure 59, a significant majority of respondents reported “limited resources” as a main challenge faced in engaging and involving the public, suggesting existing allocations of funding to PIE are not sufficient for the type or quantity of activity needed or desired. This – alongside the largely modest investments in PIE – demonstrates that, while its importance is widely acknowledged, consistent financial commitment to PIE remains limited.

Figure 59. Percentages of total infrastructure funding devoted to PIE activities (counts; n=63)

11.4 Measuring PIE impact and influence

Most respondents have adopted some form of measurement to understand the impact and influence of their PIE activities, though approaches remain diverse and, in many cases, are still evolving (Figure 60). Participation metrics are the most common method, used by two-fifths of respondents, providing a straightforward measure of reach and engagement levels across events, workshops and consultations. Impact assessments are used by a little less than a fifth of organisations, primarily in academic and charity sectors, to evaluate how public input influences governance, research or other outcomes.

and communication effectiveness, while a smaller group track behavioural or attitudinal changes to gauge longer-term outcomes. Several respondents, particularly newer or smaller ones, reported that their measurement processes are still being developed, often relying on informal feedback, central trust oversight, or maturity assessments of engagement practice. In narrative responses, some organisations noted that PIE assessment is done “elsewhere”, for example by other teams closer to the research. A number of infrastructures also noted that, in their scope of operations, measurement of PIE impact was not applicable.

Engagement analytics, adopted by just over a quarter of respondents, offer more data-driven insights into audience interaction

These findings suggest that although systematic evaluation of PIE is still emerging, there is a growing effort across the TRE ecosystem to formalise how public input effectively contributes to transparency, accountability and the responsible use of sensitive data for research.

Figure 60. Methods used by research infrastructures to measure the impact and influence of PIE activities (n=63)

12 Landscape trends

This review builds in part on the insights of previous work [1][2] to try to understand how research with sensitive data in the UK is changing over time. In particular, how it is responding to an ongoing shift from a data distribution model, where researchers download de-identified data to their local systems, to a data access model, where researchers access data remotely within secure computing environments.

Previous work has highlighted the growth of the sensitive data infrastructure ecosystem over time coinciding with an increasing recognition of the need for established standards. This includes standards around interoperability to harmonise diverse data resources, facilitate effective research collaboration and maintain sustainable research infrastructure service provision. Consistent throughout has been the underpinning principle of trustworthiness, and the need to continuously earn public confidence and maintain social license to deliver public benefit.

As previous reviews highlight, the UK research and data infrastructure communities have been at the forefront of safe, secure and trustworthy use of sensitive data within TREs over the last two decades. They continue to provide global leadership in supporting interdisciplinary research using sensitive data for public benefit. It is possible to make comparisons between reviews and draw insights into how the TRE ecosystem is changing over time. However, in some cases these are loosely held given differences in the questions asked between reviews and at times supplementing with qualitative insights from the authors' collective experience, rather than purely the data itself.

That said, when comparing between reviews, there are several trends or patterns worth highlighting:

- Total responses to both reviews (63 in 2025 and 68 in 2023) speak to a relatively stable set of organisations within the TRE ecosystem, and little variance between reviews in the sectors across which these organisations exist.
- Comparing organisational distribution across the four nations of the UK shows a relatively stable picture.

In terms of the types of data that the TRE Service Providers (n=47 in this review) support safe access to, "Smart data" is a new category that has become more prominent since the previous review. Among other data types, use of health data has remained consistently high, commercial data use is slightly increased, and both administrative and "other" data have seen significant increases in their use (notable in the "other" category in the 2025 survey are medical imaging and "omics" data).

	TRE SERVICE PROVIDERS			
	This review (2025)		Previous review (2023)	
	N = 47		N = 45	
Health data	42	88%	40	89%
Administrative data	32	67%	24	53%
Smart data	14	29%	-	-
Commercial data	14	29%	10	22%
Other data	11	23%	2	4%

Figure 61. Distribution of organisations across the UK

The number of annual projects hosted by TRE Service Providers shows interesting changes at both ends of the range, with a significant increase in the “0-25” range and a notable increase in the “more than 500” range when compared to the previous review (Figure 62). This is likely a result of, at the “0-25” range, a maturing of some of the ‘newer’ TRE Service Providers coming into the ecosystem over the last few years; and a combination of an uptick in project demand and being captured for the first time in the latest review for some of the large, incumbent TREs.

result of a cohort of ‘newer’ TREs maturing over the last few years. We can observe that the 11 TREs in the NHS England Secure Data Environment Network were not operational at the time of the 2023 survey.

As with the number of annual projects, the number of monthly users shows a significant increase in the 11-50 user range, possibly a

In terms of TRE Service Provider infrastructure provision among respondents, on-premises implementations have risen slightly, up five percentage points since the previous review, with “pure” public cloud provision shrinking and more “hybrid” platforms being adopted. There is a notable increase in the use of specialist platform providers, either stand-alone or in combination with other platforms.

Figure 62. Numbers of annual projects reported by TRE Service Providers in this review and in the previous review

Figure 63. Numbers of monthly users reported by TRE Service Providers in 2025 (left) and 2023 (right)

Figure 64. Infrastructure in use by TRE Service Providers reported in 2025 (left) and 2023 (right)

A limitation of the previous review was that it allowed only a single selection of ‘role’ within the ecosystem (see Section 5.4). This review asked deeper questions of the complex, interwoven ecosystem and captured that organisations often hold multiple roles, with almost two thirds of respondents self-identifying with more than a single role.

The share of TRE Service Providers offering advanced capabilities in high performance computing (HPC) and graphics processing units (GPUs) for more specialised, high-capacity processing demands has increased overall. This shows a significant bias towards GPU, with an increase of 23 percentage points compared to the previous review. Given the trend more broadly towards data-intensive workloads such as machine learning, this is unsurprising.

Figure 65. Percentage of TRE Service Providers offering advanced computing capabilities (HPC and GPU), 2023 survey and 2025 survey

13 Summary

This review of the TRE landscape in the UK reveals an evolving ecosystem that is central to the nation's sensitive data research infrastructure. TREs are expanding in number, scale and complexity, with strong representation from academic and public sector organisations. Most operate under well-established governance and security frameworks, adopting standards such as ISO 27001, and adoption of the relatively new SATRE specification as a TRE template is notable.

While health data remains the primary research focus, there is growing integration of administrative, smart and commercial datasets. Cloud and hybrid infrastructures are increasingly used, though on-premises hosting remains prevalent for security and compliance reasons. Public involvement and engagement (PIE) efforts are widespread but modestly funded, with growing emphasis on formal impact measurement. Overall, TREs are becoming more interoperable, transparent and strategically aligned toward scalability, federation and innovation.

TREs anticipate significant growth and transformation over the next two to three years, with responses revealing a clear focus on expansion, automation and interoperability. A large majority expect to increase both the scale and diversity of their datasets, incorporating new data types such as longitudinal, multimodal and administrative data to better support complex research needs. Around half of respondents highlighted plans to enhance automation, particularly in data ingress, output checking and user workflows, to improve efficiency and scalability.

Many TREs, especially within academic and public sector contexts, plan to expand infrastructure capabilities, including integration with high-performance computing and public-cloud-based platforms, while others are developing advanced data catalogues and visualisation tools. Collaboration and federation also emerged as strong themes, with several

TREs aiming to connect through federated networks or shared platforms to support cross-organisational research and AI-driven analysis. There is also a strategic push towards market segmentation, accreditation and expanding public sector offerings, reflecting an ambition to mature into more sustainable, interoperable and user-focused infrastructures.

The findings highlight a dynamic TRE landscape marked by both maturity and diversity. Organisations are strengthening their governance, security and technical frameworks while balancing innovation with compliance.

The sector demonstrates clear momentum toward standardisation, automation and collaborative models that support federated research. However, disparities persist in capability, resourcing and PIE, suggesting that further coordination and investment are needed to ensure consistent national coverage. As TREs continue to evolve, their role as trusted, secure enablers of data-driven research will remain vital to the UK's scientific and policy advancement.

13.1 Observations for future surveys

In compiling this analysis, we have made a number of observations relevant for future surveys:

1 ADDRESSING THE "LONG TAIL"

We have confidence that this survey captured the "big players" in the TRE landscape, but we also suspect we have missed a significant number of smaller TREs. Getting a better handle on these, and hence a better estimate of the overall population we sample, is something to plan for.

2 MEASURING INDUSTRY ENGAGEMENT

This survey (and previous ones) have focused very much on academic research users of TRE services. Our funding questions, for example, are heavily biased towards the UKRI research councils. Introducing questions better able to resolve between kinds of user and types of project will help understand broader use beyond the academic base.

3 BETTER RESOLVING SOURCES OF FUNDING

On a related note, introducing questions which better resolve sources of funding and disambiguate them from models of funding will help clarify both user-types and TRE business models. We do recognise that designing straightforward questions around funding for very different kinds of organisation is challenging.

4 MOVING AWAY FROM THE THREE "SERVICE CLASSES" (TRE SERVICE PROVIDER, TRE PLATFORM PROVIDER AND DATA PROVIDER)

Moving to a finer-grained model based around capabilities may help clarify functional overlaps in the questions set and be easier to answer. The "zone" model being introduced into the SATRE specification (and currently reflected in the UK TRE Community Glossary⁵) is one possible approach. Indeed, aligning future surveys with the structures and terminology of SATRE more generally would be sensible.

5 RETIRING DETAILED TECHNICAL QUESTIONS

The answers to some of the detailed technical questions provided little insight and little of interest to include in this report. A better approach will be to retire those questions in favour of increased detail around inter-TRE capabilities (federation, federated analytics, federated machine learning) and related complexities such as the automation or semi-automation of disclosure checks for transfers between TREs.

6 EXPLORING INCREASE IN AI USE WITHIN TREs

A final area of technical detail to explore more thoroughly is the likely increase in the development, training and evaluation of AI and machine learning models within TREs, whether created through federated learning or entirely in individual TREs. Aspects to cover will probably include the additional complexities of data preparation, advanced disclosure and risk control for model export, and the potential deployment and hosting of models within TREs and their provision as new capabilities for researchers to use in approved projects.

⁵ See <https://glossary.uktre.org/en/latest/>

14 Acknowledgements

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